

MODERN TECHNOLOGIES AND FEATURES OF THEIR USE IN ELEMENTARY MATHEMATICS CLASSES FOR PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

Khoidarova F.M.

Independent researcher at the Institute for
Retraining and Advanced Training of
Directors and Specialists of Preschool
Educational Organizations

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19212456>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 19th March 2026

Accepted: 21st March 2026

Online: 23rd March 2026

KEYWORDS

*preschool education, elementary
mathematics, modern
technologies, interactive
methods, digital education,
visual and sensory*

ABSTRACT

This thesis analyzes the importance, effectiveness, and methodological features of using modern technologies in the formation of elementary mathematical concepts in preschool children. It also highlights the impact of digital tools on the development of children's thinking.

Modern technologies are also entering mathematics education. Interactive games, electronic programs, and multimedia tools help children master mathematical concepts. However, the use of technologies should be appropriate for the age and psychophysiological characteristics of children. It is advisable for technical tools to complement traditional pedagogical methods and be used as an auxiliary tool, not the main one.

Modern technologies and their use

Technology type	Examples	Advantages	Restrictions	Usage procedure
Interactive games	Mathematical programs	Interest, interactivity	Eye health	No more than 15 minutes
Multimedia	Video lessons, animation	Visualization	Passive perception	Along with the main lesson
E-books	Interactive stories	Individual pace	Technical connection	As additional material
Educational programs	Mathematical simulators	Repetition, self-control	Lack of social contact	In personal work
Graphic editors	Simple drawing programs	Creative approach	Complexity	With a large group

Modern pedagogical research has shown that the importance of developing mathematical concepts at an early age plays a crucial role in ensuring the successful development of children in later stages of education []. The problem of developing the cognitive activity of older preschool children through the formation of elementary mathematical concepts is relevant. It is necessary to take into account the pedagogical and

psychological characteristics of the formation of elementary mathematical concepts in older preschool children, their age and individual characteristics.

Teaching elementary mathematical concepts to preschool children The formation of knowledge is associated with a number of psychological and pedagogical characteristics that determine the speed, quality, and stability of knowledge acquisition. These characteristics reflect typical patterns of cognitive development, motivational factors for learning, as well as the role of emotional experience and individual differences. Their understanding allows for the development of effective methods that help preschoolers develop sustainable skills and concepts in mathematics. Age-related patterns of cognitive development: At the age of 5-7, children experience rapid development of thinking, memory, and attention, which significantly affects the ability to master mathematical concepts. According to Jean Piaget's theory, during this period, children move from the preoperational stage to the concrete operational stage, which is manifested in the ability to think logically and manipulate objects in the mind. Children are beginning to understand the concepts of quantity, consistency, and relationship. However, their reasoning is largely based on concrete objects and may have difficulty understanding abstract concepts. Therefore, the use of visual and sensory materials is especially important for the successful acquisition of elementary mathematical concepts.

Conclusion

In general, the individual characteristics of children: each child has a different speed and method of learning. A differentiated approach based on individual characteristics allows children to learn at their own pace by using visual, auditory or tactile methods of perception. It is necessary that technical means serve as a complement to traditional pedagogical methods, and be used as an auxiliary tool, not the main one.

List of used literature:

- 1.Mavlonov.N.Sh Principles of applying the distance learning system to the educational process. // "Methodology of professional disciplines". Tashkent 2019-September 9(106)
- 2.Kadirova.F.R Preschool pedagogy textbook-T.:2019.-12b
3. The concept of modernization of Russian education in the period until 2010. //Vestnik obrazovania. -1993. — No. 2.
- 4.Kulyutkina.Yu.N Modelirovanie pedagogicheskikh situatsiy /Pod ed..-M.: Pedagogika, 1981.-120p.